

Stephan Wensveen has a Masters degree in Industrial Design Engineering. Currently he is working in the department of Industrial Design at Delft University of Technology on his PhD-project, called Emotionally Intelligent Products. He likes to surf as well.

Introduction

Try to remember how your alarm clock woke you up this morning. Now imagine a completely different situation; say after a night out and only five hours of sleep or the time you had to go to the airport at six in the morning. Waking up is a vulnerable experience that may colour the rest of your day, yet the accompanying product, the alarm clock, is not aware of the different contexts of waking up. Wouldn't it be possible to design an alarm clock that could support, or adapt its behaviour to, the different emotional experiences of a user waking up?

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Here lies a challenge for industrial designers. Instead of designing 'just' functional products we should focus on designing for experiencing (Sanders, 1999) or designing a context for experience (Overbeeke et al, 1999), as we like to call it. This new focus needs new methods to access the user's experience. If we can access and capture the experience of a user we can use this information and inspiration for new designs.

In the case of a context for waking up we need to know the emotional aspects of the user's experience before designing ways how the alarm clock can detect and express these emotions and act in an intelligent way to that information.

Capturing the user's experience of waking up

New methods for capturing an experience face some interesting challenges.

The right context

It is not appropriate to invite yourself in somebody's bedroom and videotape his emotions when he wakes up. Just as it is not useful to invite someone with his alarm clock into a lab situation. Capturing experiences has to be done in the right context, by the user himself in his own environment.

During the event...

...and not after. This is especially true for emotions. The emotion has to be captured while it happens.

Information and inspiration

The new method should not just produce information about the user's past and current experiences. It also needs to challenge the participant to

imagine and dream about desired experiences. And thus provide inspiration for innovative designs.

Designer driven

Traditional design research is mostly set up, carried out and analysed by people other than the designer, e.g. people from human factors or market researchers. But this new method should facilitate exchange between the people who experience products, interfaces, systems and spaces and the people who design for experiencing (Sanders, 1999). Therefore the designer must play an important role in the making and analysing of the ingredients of this new method.

Multi-sensorial

Verbal questions alone cannot stimulate people to explore their emotions and experiences nor can words describe them fully. We need images to feed their imaginations. We also use images of facial expressions to make it easier for people to describe their feelings (Figure 1). This method for measuring emotions through images of facial expressions is currently under development (Desmet et al, 1999). Images are also essential in giving a visual impression of the different contexts in which people wake up. With sound being one of the strongest means for waking up, we need auditory information about the experience as well.

Playful and creative

Keeping in line with the concept of designing a context for experience this new method should generate a positive experience as well. If people can express their experience in a playful and creative way their focus will shift from their current needs to dreams and wishes that are inspirational for future designs. Trading rigour for relevance (Sanders, 1999)

Too much rigour will flatten the phenomenon you are researching. We need rich feedback when researching experiences so what the new method will lack in validity it will gain in relevance for the designer/researcher.

Probes To capture the user's experience of waking up we brought 'probes' in the right context, the user's bedroom (Gaver et al., 1999).

Our probe is a package (Figure 2) containing different tasks, coloured pens, question cards, a diary, an audio recorder and a disposable camera.

Figure 1: The facial expressions of emotion, with arousal (level of excitement) on the vertical axis and valence (negative/positive) on the horizontal axis.

Figure 3: Portraits used in family tree.

Diary

The central task in the probe is a small diary in which the participants are asked to monitor their day. The questions relate to what time they got up, what their plans are for the rest of the day and how their day has been. They have to mark images of facial expressions with different coloured pens to indicate how they 25 feel about it (Figure 1).

Figure 2: The probe.

Family tree

The participant is asked to imagine that his current and ideal alarm clock can have parents and inherit their characters. Who would they be? For this purpose he is provided with portraits (Figure 3) which he can stick on a family tree postcard.

Sound and images

The probe also contains a disposable photographic camera and an audio recorder. The participants are asked to explore and capture their experience of waking up by making pictures and recording sounds: sounds and images of themselves, their alarm clock, their bedroom, something pleasant, something irritating, something relaxing or beautiful. They are also asked to record sounds and images with which they want to wake up in different situations.

Emotional advertising

People attribute emotions to products (Reeves and Nass, 1996). To investigate how the participant experiences products, a different task was set up. He is asked to choose his most and least desirable product out of four different products. This question is asked for seven different product categories: alarm clocks, bedrooms, televisions, computers, telephones, diaries, and pets (Figure 4). After making his choice, he is asked to promote his most desirable product with advertisement slogans such as those in Figure 5. The slogans do not concern functional aspects but emotional character traits, both positive and negative. Of his least desirable product out of the four products he is asked to express what he really thinks about it, using the same set of slogans.

Results The following results are based on 10 probes.

Diary

When analysing each day of a person's diary and looking carefully at the facial expressions you can empathise with the person going through each day. It gives you a good feel for how people experience waking up. And comparing people's diaries gives you a feel for the differences between people concerning their emotional experiences and their daily rhythms.

When analysing all of the diaries together you get more general information on how sleeping and waking up colours the rest of your day.

Figure 4:
A set of products.

<i>curious</i>	NIEUWSGIERIG	STOMPZINNIG	<i>stupid</i>
<i>...slightly impulsive</i>	...en een tikje impulsief	VRIENDELIJK	<i>friendly</i>
<i>full of understanding</i>	VOL BEGRIP	nogal HUMEURIG	<i>rather moody</i>
<i>extra emotions</i>	XTRA EMOTIE	TROTS op zichzelf	<i>proud of itself</i>
<i>strictly business</i>	ZEER ZAKELIJK	? ONDERZOEKEND?	<i>investigating</i>
<i>incomprehensible</i>	ONBEGRIJPELIJK	ENERGIEK	<i>energetic</i>
<i>surprising!</i>	Verrassend!	GEHOORZAAM	<i>obedient</i>
<i>full of interest</i>	VOL INTERESSE	BANGERIK	<i>scary pants</i>
<i>always cheerful</i>	Altijd vrolijk	Hulpeloos	<i>helpless</i>
<i>I nag too much</i>	ik ZEUR teveel	AMUSANT	<i>amusing</i>
<i>certainty above all</i>	Zekerheid boven alles!	ONVERSTOORBAAR	<i>undisturbed</i>
<i>never not</i>	100% INTELLIGENT NOOIT NIET	VERTROUWD	<i>trusted</i>

Figure 5:
Some of the
advertisement
slogans.

When you wake up at a later than usual time it positively influences your emotion in the morning ($R=0.284$ $p<0.05$) and even stronger in the evening ($r=0.348$ $p<0.01$). The amount of sleep has a bigger influence on how you feel in the morning ($r=0.354$ $p<0.01$) and in the evening ($r=0.502$ $p<0.001$). So an emotionally intelligent alarm clock should know the waking up time but also the amount of sleep one had.

Family tree

This task was done by 24 people.

Who are the parents of your current alarm clock?

- 12.5% Stalin ("my alarm clock is a dictator")
- 12.5% tv-news anchorman ("a bit boring but reliable")
- 10.4% a golden retriever ("as a loyal companion")
- 10.4% a rooster ("a natural and reliable alarm")
- 8.3% a professor ("intelligent, but a bit absent-minded")
- 6.3% Muhammad Ali ("it beats me awake with no mercy")

Who are the parents of your ideal alarm clock?

- 29.2% the sun ("a natural gradual way of waking up")
- 10.4% Dalai Lama ("waking up in a peaceful, tranquil way")
- 10.4% a rooster ("a natural and reliable alarm")
- 8.3% a golden retriever ("as a loyal companion")
- 6.3% Mickey Mouse ("a friendly, happy way of waking up")

Sound and images

The participants told me that these tasks were the hardest to do. The informational sounds, their voice and the alarm sound and the images of themselves, their alarm clock and their bedroom were easy to capture. The more inspirational and creative tasks, like capturing something beautiful, something pleasant and things that had to do with different situations were harder to do. Participants wondered what I wanted to see and hear and how that would be useful for me. The results were useful though, informational and inspirational. The sounds and images helped me especially to immerse in the user's experience and helped me to try to relive it as good as possible.

Emotional advertising

In this task there were 7 product categories, each with 4 products and 46 slogans to stick on the chosen products. With only 10 participants it is not possible yet to make any conclusive comments about this task. The most used slogans for their ideal products were; everything under control, easy to handle, 100% intelligent, intimate, relaxed, certainty above all, pleasant, loyal, now even smarter and trusted. The most used negative slogans were; incomprehensible, boring, irritating, helpless, I nag too much and smart-ass.

My ideal alarm clock needs to know...

People were asked to imagine that they had an extremely smart alarm clock. The given pictures showed different possibilities of information, but they could add their own ideas as well. They had to give their preferences by sticking coloured dots on the different pictures. Figure 6 shows how the dots were distributed.

Figure 6: My ideal alarm clock needs to know...

The probe proved to be a good tool to capture the experience of waking up. Its ingredients returned rich feedback from each individual, which helped to empathise with each person and gave a good feeling for the context in which they wake up. The results of some tasks provided more general information about people waking up, like the diary and the questions in them. Some were more inspirational like the task with the 'parents' of the user's ideal alarm clock. The success of probes is in their ingredients, but what is more important is how the designer uses the results for future designs of contexts for experience.

Future research

The information and inspiration the probes generated will be used for the next step in designing an emotionally intelligent alarm clock. What we need now are ways for the alarm clock to detect and express the emotional state of the user. Our approach is to design a product in such a way that it affords actions, which are rich in emotional content. The user can then perceive the possibility of acting in an emotionally expressive way and act how he feels, so the product can detect the emotional state through the user's actions.

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Figure 7: The pin alarm

Example

The design by two of our students, Hellman and Ypma (Figure 7) has multiple pins. Each pin represents a few minutes. If the user wants a great deal of sleep, she can make this known to the alarm clock by pressing as many pins as possible at the same time. The display then shows that she will wake up at, say, 10 o'clock instead of half past 8. So she has pushed too many pins and has to pull out some pins to subtract time to reach half past 8. These actions will give the alarm clock an idea of how much sleep the user actually wants. It also knows how precisely she set and chose the alarm time and adapts its behaviour according to all the information.

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